

GROWTH AND INSTABILITY IN AREA, PRODUCTION AND PRODUCTIVITY OF MAJOR PULSES IN MAHARASHTRA

G.M. Bodakhe*, R.D. Shelke¹, S. H. Kamble²

Ph.D Scholar, Department of Agricultural Economics,

V.N.M.K.V., Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.

ganeshbodakhe11@gmail.com*

Associate professor, Department of Agricultural Economics,

College of Agriculture, Latur, V.N.M.K.V., Parbhani¹ Maharashtra, India.

Assistant professor, Department of Agricultural Economics,

College of Agriculture, Latur, V.N.M.K.V., Parbhani² Maharashtra, India.

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Abstract

The present study has been attempted to analyse the growth rate and instability in area, production and productivity of major pulses in Maharashtra. The growth in the area, production and productivity of pulses in Maharashtra state was estimated using the compound growth function. The necessary secondary data were collected for a period of 30 years from 1990-91 to 2020-21, which was further divided into three sub-period decade wise i.e period-I (1990-91 to 1999-00), period-II (2000-01 to 2009-10) and period-III (2010-11 to 2019-20). The compound growth rates of area, production and productivity of pulses was worked out by using exponential function. To measure the instability in area, production and productivity, an index of instability was used as a measure of variability. The instability index developed by Cuddy and Della was also be used for estimating instability index. Results have shown that, pulse area in state considerably increased. Area under pigeon pea registered a significant growth rate of 1.01 per cent and area under chick pea registered a significant growth rate of 4.41 per cent. . Growth rate for area, production and productivity of pigeon pea and chickpea was found to be significantly positive. The production of chickpea increased more due to area effect and the production of pigeon pea increased because of improvement in the yield and its interaction with area.

Keywords: Pulses, Compound Growth rate, Instability, Cuddy Della Valle Index.

Introduction

Pulses are important sources of proteins for the vegetarians in India. Its complement the staple cereals in the diets with proteins, essential amino acids, vitamins and minerals. It contains 22-24% of protein, which is almost more than double the protein in wheat and three times that of rice and also an important crop in farm production system as they improve fertility of soil by adding nitrogen in the soil. These pulses mainly include chickpea, pigeon pea, lentil, moong bean, urd bean and field pea.

The share of pulses to total food grain basket is around 9-10 per cent and is a serious and inexpensive source of plant-based proteins, vitamins and minerals. India occupies the first place, both in terms of the area (34%) and production (26%) of pulses in the world. Pulses were grown over more than 29 million ha of area and recorded the highest ever production of 25.23 million tonnes with a productivity level of 841 kg/ha during the year 2021-22 The country is leading importer and about 20% of the total pulses demands are met by imports only due to the stagnant production over the years (shukla and Mishra, 2018). The major pulse producing states in the country are Madhya Pradesh (33%) followed by Maharashtra (13%), Rajasthan (12%), Uttar Pradesh (9%), Karnataka (8%) and Andhra Pradesh (5%). Maharashtra ranks third amongst the Indian states in terms of area and production under pulses. The productivity of pulses in the state is very low (420 kg/ha) as compared to the other leading states. (Source: Directorate of Economics & Statistics-2022)

Pulses are an significant group of food crops that play a vital role to attain food and nutritional security and also tackle environmental challenges. It was with this background that the growth and instability in area, production and yield of selected pulse crop was studied in the state.

Materials and methods

The study was depend mainly on the secondary data i.e. time series data on area, production and yield of pigeon pea, chickpea and total pulses in the state of Maharashtra. The data for a period of 30 years from 1990-91 to 2020-21, were collected from various published sources like Maharashtra Agricultural Statistics at Glance etc. The entire study was split three sub-period decade wise i.e period-I (1990-91 to 1999-00), period-II (2000-01 to 2009-10) and period-III (2010-11 to 2019-20).

Analytical tools**Growth Rate**

To obtain a measure of growth rate of pulses in terms of area, production and productivity, trend function was used. In the present study, two sample trend equations was tried.

The linear growth rate of pulses in terms of area, production and productivity was estimated with the help of the following linear function.

$$Y_t = a + bt + u$$

Where,

Y_t = the area/production/ productivity of pulses in the year

't'

a = intercept

b = Regression coefficient

t = time period (year 1,2,3.....t)

u = random variable of error

The compound growth rate of area, production and productivity of pulses crop were worked out by fitting an exponential function as given below

$$Y_t = ab^t$$

Where,

Y = Area, Production and productivity

a = Intercept

b = Regression coefficient

t = Time period (years) From the coefficient values,

the rates of compound growth will be work out by using the formula,

$$CGR(r) = [\text{Antilog}(\log b) - 1] \times 100$$

Where,

r = Compound growth rate in per cent.

Coefficient of variation

$$\text{Coefficient of variation} = \frac{\sigma}{\bar{x}} \times 100$$

Where,

σ = Standard deviation

\bar{x} = Mean

Cuddy and Della instability index (CDVI)

In order to study the variability in area, production and productivity of major pulses in Maharashtra state, an instability index by Cuddy and Della (1978) was used.

$$\text{Instability index} = CV \times \sqrt{1 - R^2}$$

Where,

CV = Coefficient of Variation

R^2 = Coefficient of determination of trend

Results And Discussion

Growth and instability in area, production and productivity of pigeon pea in Maharashtra state

The result of growth and instability analysis for the Maharashtra state were presented in Table 4.1. Over the period of 1990-91 to 2019-20, growth of pigeon pea were positively significant. The area of pigeon pea has been increased at the rate of 1.01 per cent per annum by compound growth. The average area in the first period was 10.26 lakh ha which was slightly increased upto 12.72 lakh ha. in the third period. The average area of Pigeon pea was 11.25 lakh ha. in overall period. The growth in area was non-significant in the period-II and period-III. The area of pigeon pea in the state was approximately static. The fluctuation was observed in between 1.74 to 5.88 per cent. The growth in production were positive and significant in overall study period. The production of Pigeon pea has been increased over the year at the rate of 2.49 per cent by compound growth. The average production of the state for overall period was 7927.60 lakh tonne. The

production of Pigeon pea in the first period was 5961.10 lakh tonne, which was increased upto 10055.55 lakh tonne in third sub-period. Except the first period, the growth in the production was non-significant. The figures of Cuddy-Della clearly states that the level of production was highly fluctuating as there figures were ranges from 17.77 per cent to 46.08 per cent. The production was unstable in overall research period.

The growth in average production were also positive and significant for overall period. The average crop yield in the first period was 579.63 per ha. which was increased upto 777.58 kg per ha. in third period. The average productivity of pigeon pea in the state for overall period was 691.84 kg/ha. All period, the growth in productivity was non-significant. For overall period, the growth in productivity was observed at the scale of 1.46 per cent per annum by compound rate. The C.D. vella values was higher in the third period indicating higher fluctuation of yield of the crop. In general the fluctuation in yield was low to high. The C.D. value were ranged from 14.33 to 39.51 per cent.

Table 4.1. Growth and instability in area, production and productivity of Pigeon pea in Maharashtra state

Estimates	Sub-Periods			Overall
	I	II	III	
Area(00'ha)				
CGR	0.32*	0.36	0.98	1.01***
Mean	10266.00	10776.90	12727.76	11256.89
SD	188.28	465.08	867.17	1214.72
CV	1.83	4.32	6.81	10.79
CD Vella	1.74	4.24	5.88	5.88
Production (000'MT)				
CGR	6.02*	2.19	3.05	2.49**
Mean	5961.10	7766.14	10055.55	7927.60
SD	1848.15	1396.69	4784.55	3416.69
CV	31.00	17.98	47.58	43.10
CD Vella	28.28	17.77	46.08	37.21
Productivity(kg/ha)				
CGR	5.85	1.82	2.05	1.46**
Mean	579.63	718.32	777.58	691.84
SD	176.67	106.76	323.63	229.88
CV	30.48	14.86	41.62	33.23
CD Vella	27.77	14.33	39.51	31.14

Note :

Period-I : 1990-91 to 1999-00

Period-II : 2000-01 to 2009-10

Period-III : 2010-11 to 2019-20

*** Significant at 01 per cent level of Significance

** Significant at 05 per cent level of Significance

* Significant at 10 per cent level of Significance

Fig 4.1. Average area, production and productivity of pigeon pea in Maharashtra state

4.2. Growth and instability in area, production and productivity of chick pea in Maharashtra state

The result of growth and instability analysis for the Maharashtra state were presented in Table 4.2. Over the period of 1990-91 to 2019-20, growth of chick pea were positively significant. The area of Chick pea has been increased at the rate of 4.41 per cent per annum by compound growth. The average area of chick pea in the first period was 7.05 lakh ha which was slightly increased upto 15.93 lakh ha. in the third period. The average area of Chick pea was 10.98 lakh ha. in overall period. The growth in area was significant in the all three periods. The area of Chick pea in the state was approximately static. The fluctuation was observed in between 05 to 08 per cent.

The growth in production of chick pea were positive and significant in overall study period. The production of chick pea has been increased over the year at the rate of 5.59 per cent by compound growth. The average production of chick pea in the state for overall period was 8259.39 lakh tonne. The production of chick pea in the

first period was 4089.90 lakh tonne, which was increased upto 13916.84 lakh tonne in third sub-period. All the study period, the growth in the production was significant. The figures of Cuddy-Della clearly states that the level of production was highly fluctuating as there figures were ranges from 21.04 per cent to 35.76 per cent. The production was unstable in overall research period.

The growth in average production of chick pea were also positive and non-significant for overall period. The average crop yield in the first period was 588.32 per ha. which was increased upto 853.27 kg per ha. in third period. The average productivity of chick pea in the state for overall period was 698.25 kg/ha. Except the second period, the growth in the production was non-significant. For overall period, the growth in productivity was observed at the scale of 1.92 per cent per annum by compound rate. The C.D. vella values was higher in the third period indicating higher fluctuation of yield of the crop. In general the fluctuation in yield was low to moderate. The C.D. value were ranged from 10.15 to 17.96 per cent.

Table 4.2. Growth and instability in area, production and productivity of chick pea in Maharashtra state

Estimates	Sub-Periods			Overall
	I	II	III	
Area(000'ha)				
CGR	5.58***	8.24***	6.54***	4.41***
Mean	7056.30	9970.30	15937.24	10987.95
SD	1396.35	2586.66	3793.72	4613.27
CV	19.79	25.94	23.80	41.98
CD Vella	12.33	11.69	15.17	18.22
Production (000'MT)				
CGR	7.00**	13.93**	8.36**	5.59***
Mean	4089.90	6771.43	13916.84	8259.39
SD	1252.08	2935.20	5263.08	5436.15
CV	30.61	43.35	37.82	65.82
CD Vella	24.46	21.04	29.48	35.76
Productivity(kg/ha)				
CGR	0.39	5.25***	1.70	1.92
Mean	588.32	653.17	853.27	698.25
SD	98.61	120.81	153.80	167.46
CV	16.76	18.50	18.03	23.98
CD Vella	15.76	10.15	17.96	16.86

Note : Period-I : 1990-91 to 1999-00

Period-II : 2000-01 to 2009-10

Period-III : 2010-11 to 2019-20

*** Significant at 01 per cent level of Significance

** Significant at 05 per cent level of Significance

* Significant at 10 per cent level of Significance

Fig 4.2. Average area, production and productivity of chick pea in Maharashtra state

Growth and instability in area, production and productivity of pulses in Maharashtra state

The result of growth and instability analysis for the Maharashtra state were presented in Table 4.3. Over the period of 1990-91 to 2019-20, growth of pulses were positively significant. The area of pulses has been increased at the rate of 0.64 per cent per annum by compound growth. The average area of Pulses in the first period was 34.11 lakh ha which was slightly increased upto 38.52 lakh ha. in the third period. The average area of Pulses was 35.91 lakh ha. in overall period. Except the second period the growth in area was significant in the two periods. The area of Pulses in the state was approximately static. The fluctuation was observed in between 03 to 33 per cent.

The growth in production of pulses were positive and significant in overall study period. The production of Pulses has been increased over the year at the rate of 2.53 per cent by compound growth. The average production of Pulses in the state for overall period was 22229.81 lakh tonne. The production of pulses in the first period was

17535.50 lakh tonne, which was increased upto 28620.71 lakh tonne in third sub-period. All the study period, the growth in the production was non-significant. The figures of Cuddy-Della clearly states that the level of production was highly fluctuating as there figures were ranges from 24 per cent to 40 per cent. The production of Pulses was unstable in overall research period.

The growth in average production of Pulses were also positive and significant for overall period. The average crop yield in the first period was 511.83 kg per ha. which was increased upto 725.44 kg per ha. in third period. The average productivity of pulses in the state for overall period was 606.53 kg/ha. Except the second period, the growth in the production was non-significant. For overall period, the growth in productivity was observed at the scale of 1.83 per cent per annum by compound rate. The C.D. vella values was higher in the second period indicating higher fluctuation of yield of the crop. In general the fluctuation in yield was moderate to high. The C.D. value were ranged from 22 to 34 per cent.

Table 4.3. Growth and instability in area, production and productivity of pulses in Maharashtra state

Estimates	Sub-Periods			Overall period
	I	II	III	
Area(00'ha)				
CGR	1.13**	-0.06	2.53*	0.64***
Mean	34119.40	31539.34	38520.40	35912.08
SD	1627.91	11395.82	4679.35	3674.66
CV	4.77	36.13	12.15	10.23
CD Vella	3.83	33.49	7.29	8.56
Production (000'MT)				
CGR	4.77	3.11	3.95	2.53**
Mean	17535.50	18896.43	28620.71	22229.81
SD	4496.39	7750.31	9833.51	8036.54
CV	25.64	41.01	34.36	36.15
CD Vella	24.22	40.50	31.69	28.49
Productivity(kg/ha)				
CGR	3.63	3.18**	1.10	1.83***
Mean	511.83	536.41	725.44	606.53
SD	119.77	202.64	183.72	159.46
CV	23.40	37.78	25.33	26.29
CD Vella	22.89	34.27	24.36	21.45

Note : Period-I : 1990-91 to 1999-00

Period-II : 2000-01 to 2009-10

Period-III : 2010-11 to 2019-20

*** Significant at 01 per cent level of Significance

** Significant at 05 per cent level of Significance

* Significant at 10 per cent level of Significance

Fig 4.3. Average area, production and productivity of pulses in Maharashtra state

Conclusions

This study was attempted to find out the growth rate and instability of area, production and productivity of pulses in Maharashtra from the secondary data for a period from 1990-91 to 2019-20. This shows that the area, production and productivity total pulses growth trends in Maharashtra was positive. In case of pigeon pea the area, production and productivity trends are positive. But in chick pea the area and production is positive while productivity is negative. The discussion made above can be concluded as the growth of area under pulses showed mixed trend in the period of study i.e. from 1991-2020. It is concluded from the above discussion that Maharashtra state was failed to achieve the stability in production of pulses.

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